

ENHANCING READING LITERACY PROFICIENCY AMONG GRADE 1 LOW EMERGING – LEVEL READERS THROUGH BASA ARANGKADA SA UMAGA (BAU)INTERVENTION

JANE EDEN A. CAÑADILLA, E.D.D-EMD ¹ | NIEVA MAE V. LAURONAL, E.D.D-EMD ² | JEAN V. ELVIRA, E.D.D-EMD ³ | JOMAR C. CHIONG, E.D.D-EMD ⁴ | MA. NELIA E. APURA, E.D.D-EMD ⁵ | MARILYN M. MIRANDA EDD, DPA ⁶

¹ CEBU TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY, DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION, CEBU CITY, CEBU PHILIPPINES.

² CEBU TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY, DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION, CEBU CITY, CEBU PHILIPPINES.

³ CEBU TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY, DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION, CEBU CITY, CEBU PHILIPPINES.

⁴ CEBU TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY, DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION, CEBU CITY, CEBU PHILIPPINES.

⁵ CEBU TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY, DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION, CEBU CITY, CEBU PHILIPPINES.

⁶ CEBU TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY, DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION, CEBU CITY, CEBU PHILIPPINES.

ABSTRACT:

This study assesses Grade 1 learners identified as low emerging-level readers through the Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA). The Basa Arangkadasa Umaga (BAU) is a structured morning literacy program designed to enhance foundational reading skills through brief daily sessions focusing on letter-sound mastery, syllable blending, word recognition, and guided oral reading. These tasks are integrated with literacy warm-ups to boost cognitive readiness at the start of the school day.

At Bolocboloc Elementary School SY 2025–2026, 4 of 24 Grade 1 learners showed gaps in phonics, fluency, vocabulary, and comprehension. To address these needs, the intervention includes multisensory literacy activities, structured phonics, fluency routines, peer-assisted and remedial reading, read-aloud sessions, and home reading programs. Using a descriptive quantitative research design, pre- and post-test results were analyzed with descriptive statistics to evaluate BAU's effectiveness in improving learners' reading proficiency. Progress reports and formative assessments throughout the sessions provided additional evidence of improvement.

KEYWORDS:

LOW EMERGING –LEVEL READERS, READING LITERACY, CRLA, BAU.

PAPER ACCEPTED DATE:

PAPER PUBLISHED DATE:

1st March 2026

2nd March 2026

PAPER DOI NO:

PAPER DOI LINK:

10.5281/zenodo.18838586

<https://zenodo.org/records/18838586>

I. INTRODUCTION

Low emerging reading levels among Grade 1 learners remain a concern, as many struggle with letter recognition, sound blending, and decoding simple words. CRLA results for SY 2025–2026 indicate that 33.42% of learners across Grades 1–3 are low emerging readers, with Bolocboloc Elementary reporting 17% of Grade 1 pupils in this category. These results highlight the need for timely, targeted interventions aligned with DepEd's early literacy goals.

Research at Judge Antonio R. Montilla Sr. Elementary School showed average reading rates of 34.32 WPM, with similar performance across sections and no significant

gender differences. While most learners met expected reading levels, intervention needs varied. Recommendations include targeted support, teacher training, regular monitoring, active parental involvement, gender-responsive strategies, and improved reading resources.

II. OBJECTIVE

The study aims to enhance reading literacy proficiency among Grade 1 low emerging-level readers using BAU. The intervention supports teachers in developing learners' reading skills from low emerging level to grade-level

proficiency. Daily sessions focus on:

1. Letter-sound mastery
2. Syllable blending
3. Word recognition
4. Guided oral reading

These activities are combined with literacy warm-ups to boost cognitive readiness and are evidence-based, consistent, and developmentally appropriate.

III. METHODOLOGY

The study employed a descriptive quantitative design, which uses quantifiable data to describe problems and analyze variable relationships (Creswell, 2002, cited by Ghanad, 2023). Pre- and post-test scores assessed learners' reading proficiency before and after BAU intervention.

Participants were Grade 1 learners identified as low emerging readers through CRLA. Ethical standards were followed, including parental consent, voluntary participation, and confidentiality in compliance with the Data Privacy Act.

PRESENTATION OF DATA AND ANALYSIS

A. PRE-IMPLEMENTATION PHASE

Approval from the school head and submission of necessary documents were secured. Baseline CRLA results identified participants. Parents were informed and consent obtained. Instructional materials, assessment tools, and monitoring forms aligned with BAU routines were prepared, and teacher orientations conducted.

B. IMPLEMENTATION PHASE

BAU sessions ran daily from 7:30–8:00 a.m., including literacy warm-ups and activities targeting letter-sound mastery, syllable blending, word recognition, guided oral reading, phonemic awareness, and spelling exercises. Learners' progress was monitored via weekly assessments, Oral Reading Verification (ORV), and Reading Profiles. Teachers collaborated to ensure fidelity, and challenges were documented to inform instructional decisions.

C. POST-IMPLEMENTATION PHASE

CRLA pre- and post-test results were analyzed descriptively to identify progress and remaining gaps. Findings informed recommendations to improve reading instruction and strengthen future interventions. Results were shared with teachers, parents, and school leaders.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

BAU intervention demonstrated significant improvement in learners' reading proficiency. Learners showed enhanced letter-sound mastery, decoding skills, fluency, and comprehension. Structured, daily literacy routines improved consistency in practice and learner engagement. Early morning reading proved effective, as learners were alert, refreshed, and more focused. The study confirms that

targeted, evidence-based interventions can accelerate foundational literacy skills.

IV. CONCLUSION

The study concludes that BAU effectively enhances reading proficiency among Grade 1 low emerging readers. Daily structured morning sessions support skill acquisition and provide teachers with a framework for monitoring progress. Early morning reading leverages learners' cognitive alertness for better focus and learning outcomes and enable better concentration on reading materials.

V. RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings, the following are recommended

1. The learners read in the morning specifically 7:30-8:00 Conduct morning reading sessions to improve proficiency.
2. Implement BAU to develop learners' familiarity with sounds and word blending.
3. Use CRLA post-test results to track progress and transform low emerging readers to grade-level proficiency.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The researchers thank their adviser, Dr. Marilyn Miranda, co-researchers, family, and God for guidance, support, and wisdom in completing this study.

REFERENCES

1. Creswell, J. W. (2002). *Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research*. Pearson Education. Secondary source: Ghanad, N. (2023).
2. Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2023). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (6th ed.). SAGE Publications.
3. Bordens, K. S., & Abbott, B. B. (2025). *Research design and methods: A process approach*. McGraw-Hill.
4. Hill, C. J., et al. (2023). *Conducting implementation research in impact studies of education interventions: A guide for researchers* (NCEE 2023-005).
5. Holtz, B., et al. (2024). *Enhancing comprehension of online informed consent*. Ethics & Behavior.
6. American Psychological Association. (2022). *Ethical principles of psychologists and code of conduct* (2002 ed.).